

Online Quality of Services of Ship Procurement License at Kesyhbandaran Utama Tanjung Perak Surabaya Office

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ABSTRACT: One of the efforts to create optimal services quickly and cheaply is by providing information technology for integrated exchange of data and information. Tanjung Perak Surabaya Main Harbormaster Office implements an online service system in accordance with the Regulation of the Minister of Transportation of the Republic of Indonesia PM Number 154 of 2015 concerning Online Syahbandar Approval Letter Services, including the service of Ship Motion Approval Letters at the Port. The government through the Ministry of Transportation developed Inaportnet, which is an internet-based electronic single service system. The Inaportnet concept is applied as a ship service system in terms of ports in the activities of arrival and departure of ships as well as plans for loading and unloading activities that can be carried out effectively and efficiently. The purpose of this research is to describe and analyze the Quality of Service for Ship Motion Permit Online at the Tanjung Perak Surabaya Main Harbormaster Office using the theory of electronic service quality by Ribbink et. al (2004). This research method is descriptive research with a qualitative approach, data collection is done by interview, observation, and documentation techniques. The results obtained are then collected, reduced, presented, and conclusions are drawn.

The results of this study indicate that the Quality of Service for Ship Motion Permits Online at the Tanjung Perak Surabaya Main Harbormaster Office shows that service quality is not optimal. It is said that it is not optimal because there are dimensions that do not meet the needs of service users, namely: there is no complaints and suggestions menu in the Inaportnet application, there is no data correction menu if an error occurs in the data input process so that service users have to process data input repeatedly, of course impede the work of shipping agents, especially in the process of applying for ship operating permits online.

KEYWORDS: Harbormaster, Inaportnet, Service Quality, Ship Motion, Surabaya.

INTRODUCTION

The port is an important facility, especially for water transportation in rivers, lakes and seas. With this transportation, the required distance will be felt more quickly, especially for the economic development of an area where the center of consumer goods production can be marketed quickly and smoothly. Apart from that, in the economic field, ports have a positive impact on the development of an isolated area, especially water areas where accessibility by land is difficult to do properly. Port services include ship services (Mooring, Mooring, Pandu, Delay and Water) and goods services (dock services and stacking services). Port services have their respective roles and are related to each other in order to support the smooth activities of ships in their activities of distributing goods. According to Shipping Law No. 17 of 2008 Article 207 Paragraph 3, Syahbandar is a government official at the port who is appointed by the Minister of Transportation and has the highest authority to carry out and carry out full supervision of the provisions of the laws and regulations to ensure the safety and security of shipping which includes implementation, supervision and law enforcement in the field of transportation waters, ports and protection of the maritime environment in ports throughout Indonesia. Syahbandar has a Kesyahbandar office or port authority with sections to carry out and supervise the provisions of the laws and regulations that have been set by the government as well as separating the functions of the Syahbandar within the port administrator's office environment.

The Tanjung Perak Surabaya Main Harbormaster Office (KSU) carries out its duties and functions based on the Minister of Transportation Regulation Number 34 of 2012 concerning the Organization and Work Procedure of the Main Harbormaster Office which has the task of carrying out supervision and law enforcement in the field of shipping safety and security, coordinating government activities at the port as well as regulation, control and supervision of port activities at commercially operated ports. Based on the circular of the Minister of Transportation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 31 of 2016 concerning Supervision and Control in Governance in the Ministry of Transportation. In the Circular, the Minister of Transportation of the Republic of

Indonesia ordered work units both at the central and regional levels to provide service information including types of services and rates in a transparent, clear and accurate manner, as well as develop information technology-based licensing services. Regarding the intended service standard, it is further emphasized in the Regulation of the Minister of Transportation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 19 of 2017 concerning Guidelines for Service Standards within the Ministry of Transportation. Especially Chapter II letter B number 5, which explains that service standards (within the Ministry of Transportation) are carried out with due observance of the Transparency Principle, namely service standards must be easily accessible to the public.

Ship services are very important in economic development, especially in Indonesia, therefore to handle the ship arrival process, experts must be prepared to handle it as well as possible. Services are part of sea transportation facilities which, as stated in Law Number 17 of 2008, are very strategic for national vision and are a means of supporting the goals of unity. Optimal services at the port will have an impact on the smooth flow of traffic and sea transportation which needs to be carried out on an ongoing basis, and continue to be improved so that the reach and services are wider to the community as well as realizing a reliable and integrated national transportation system. Besides that, optimal port services need to be maintained and improved so that the important thing that needs to be worked out is to avoid long waiting times and low queuing system utilities (Sutria, Dirhamsyah, Jufriyanto 2022).

The Tanjung Perak Surabaya Main Harbormaster Office also implements an online service system in accordance with the Regulation of the Minister of Transportation of the Republic of Indonesia PM Number 154 of 2015 concerning Online Syahbandar Approval Letter Services, which is explained in Chapter I Article 3 which explains online services consisting of: ship approval letter services Entering the Port (Clearance-in); the service of Letter of Approval for Ship Movement at the Port; and Sailing Approval Letter services (Clearance-out/ Port Clearance). One of the efforts to create optimal services quickly and cheaply is by providing information technology for integrated data and information exchange where the government through the Ministry of Transportation developed Inaportnet, namely an internet-based electronic single service system. The implementation of the Inaportnet concept as a ship service system in port matters as stated in the Regulation of the Minister of Transportation of the Republic of Indonesia Number PM 157 of 2015, is intended so that the arrival and departure of ships as well as plans for loading and unloading activities can be carried out effectively and efficiently.

Inaportnet according to the regulation of the Minister of Transportation of the Republic of Indonesia Number PM 157 of 2015 is an Internet/web-based electronic single service system to integrate a standard port information system in serving ships and goods physically from all agencies or stakeholders related to the port. The Inaportnet system implemented at this time has met a standard and is easy to implement. If users have felt the benefits after using the Inaportnet system, it will provide satisfaction to these users. User satisfaction is very important for the development of an information system. The level of user satisfaction of a system can be used as a reference in the process of developing the system itself, as well as to find out the advantages and disadvantages of the system being implemented or implemented.

Tanjung Perak Port in Surabaya is the largest and second busiest port in Indonesia after Jakarta's Tanjung Priok port. This is because apart from being a connecting gate for eastern Indonesia, it is also because economic growth in the East Java Province region has increased, thus triggering an increase in the flow of distribution of goods to and from the East Java region for both domestic goods and international trade. The Tanjung Perak port service in Surabaya besides serving the arrival/departure of ships (clearance in/out) as well as for planned loading and unloading activities also serves moving ships, moving ships is often called ship maneuvering. In general, a ship's maneuvering permit is a permit given to the ship to move from one pier to another or vice versa, in other words, the ship is given a permit to carry out the movement only in the port of Tanjung Perak. Ship movement permits are given by the Syahbandar office to ship owners or agents if the ship meets several important conditions that have been fulfilled. A ship maneuvering permit is no less important than a sailing approval letter and other documents because this ship maneuvering license is an important document that must be owned by a ship in order to be able to carry out berthing movements from the berthing area to the wharf and vice versa from the wharf to the mooring area. must meet important requirements set by the government. Besides that, for the safety of environmental health and safety of navigation when carrying out ship movements so that there are no collisions in the port area.

The granting of permits for ship maneuvering through the Inaportnet system is given by the Head of Harbormaster to Shipping Agents/ship operators through stages involving General Services, Head of Sailing Safety Division, Head of Bandar Orderly Section, and Executing Officers. The granting of permits from 2018 to 2022 has seen an increase in permits for incoming and

outgoing vessels. Meanwhile, for the transfer of ships in the Port of Tanjung Perak, Surabaya, the granting of permits to move ships from 2019 to 2022 has decreased. If seen from the chart above, there is a possibility that problems will arise which will cause the granting of relocation permits to decrease. Submission of ship maneuvering permits can be done manually or online, due to the development of advances in information technology and the digitization of many shipping agents who make submissions online. Based on the researcher's analysis, in 2021 the last application for ship maneuvering permits online has decreased.

In 2021 ship handling approvals have decreased, this could be due to users (shipping agents) not understanding how to use the Inaportnet system or there could also be problems with the Inaportnet system itself. Empirically the cause of the Inaportnet system problem is that this application found an error due to a bad internet connection and the size capacity of the ship's documents is too large. The existence of an error system in the application should be immediately handled by the coordinator on duty, because this is related to the Responsiveness dimension in e-service quality theory. Shipping agent operators lack understanding in using the Inaportnet application to fill in the recommended data in the ship's maneuvering permit, besides that the completeness of the documents as a prerequisite for submitting permits has not been changed, shipping agent operators upload the same documents every time they apply for a permit through the Inaportnet application. Of course, the process of submitting ship maneuvers with the same documents does not get approval from the Harbormaster's Office, the harbormaster's officer will inform the shipping agent again to upload the latest document. Problems with these documents will affect the process of moving ships, it becomes inefficient in the end and takes longer. Whereas online services should make services easy, concise, and fast. With this problem, it is indeed the fundamental cause of the decline in the granting of ship maneuvering permits at the Tanjung Perak Surabaya Main Harbormaster Office, Surabaya.

In the Inaportnet-based online service, there are still several obstacles in the Service Level Agreement and the form of the Inaportnet application that is accessed by shipping agents, which hinders the work of sea transport service users. In its own development, the service system has not yet achieved the desired results. Various responses from users of sea transportation services tend to show that Inaportnet services sometimes make it difficult for them to work. When a shipping agent inputs the same data every time he submits an approval letter for ship maneuvering online through the Inaportnet application, the data is a duplicate of the previous data that has been input. So that when the officer performs the verification, letters or certificates that have expired/expired will be found, then the data is returned and it is recommended to re-upload it. This causes delays in the online verification process, while shipping agents want the process to run smoothly without any problems. Based on the problems that have been raised, that the difficulties experienced by service users do not meet the Customization dimension in the theoretical concept of e-service quality.

The Tanjung Perak Surabaya Main Harbormaster Office always carries out various policies that can provide excellent and quality service, in order to be able to maximize service to the public including private shipping agents. The practice of administering public services (public service) is one of the manifestations of the function of the state apparatus as a servant of society as well as a servant of the state. The function of this service is directed at meeting the needs of the community as well as creating social justice in the community, so that the government will be able to create a better life for its people (Ulum, 2018). As part of a government organization that serves the public or private shipping agents, the Tanjung Perak Surabaya Main Harbormaster Office is required to continue to improve the quality of its services so that service user communities including private sea transportation companies (Agents) feel satisfied with the services provided so that the Agent will be more comfortable in utilizing the services at the Main Kesyahbandaran Tanjung Perak Surabaya Office. If the perceived service is as expected, then the service quality is perceived as good and satisfying. If the service received exceeds consumer expectations, then service quality is perceived as an ideal quality. Conversely, if the service received is lower than expected, then the service quality is perceived as bad. Thus whether or not the quality of service depends on the ability of service providers to consistently meet consumer expectations.

In order to be able to provide satisfaction to the community/service users, the service provider/parties who serve must have the same perceptions and expectations that make it possible to be satisfied. The service provider determines what details are attempted to provide satisfaction to the customer, at least it can be close to or very small difference from what the customer expects (Mulyawan, 2016). Furthermore, the development of electronic government is an effort to develop governance based on (using) information technology (internet) in order to improve the quality of public services effectively and efficiently.

According to Ribbink et. al (2004) in Prasetyo et al (2021), customer satisfaction is a very important thing to get. This satisfaction is very dependent on service quality, which in this case is called e-service quality, which is felt by consumers when

making transactions. Satisfaction can be obtained by consumers, one of which is through satisfying service both in terms of design/appearance, convenience, and also a quick response to any complaints felt by service users. Therefore, to increase service user satisfaction is by improving service quality, also known as e-service quality. According to Ribbink et. al (2004) this relates to ease of use (ease of use), attractive layout and design (e-scape), response and response to service users (responsiveness), complete info (customization) and security of service users (assurance). .

Based on the conditions that occurred at the Tanjung Perak Surabaya Main Harbormaster Office, this is in accordance with the theory put forward by Ribbink et. al (2004) that e-service quality or also known as E-ServQual is a new version of Service Quality (ServQual). E-ServQual was developed to evaluate a service provided on the Internet network. E-Service Quality is defined as the extension of a site's ability to facilitate service users effectively and efficiently. Following are the dimensions of e-service quality according to Ribbink et. al (2004) there are 5 (five) dimensions, namely: Ease of Use, E-Scape, Customization, Responsiveness, and Assurance. Whereas the appearance of the Inaportnet website which is usually accessed by shipping agents for the processing of ship maneuvering permits is very simple and easy to use. On the user login page, service users (shipping agents) only need to enter their registered email address and password. Furthermore, if the login has been done, the user will enter on the Dashboard page. There are menus of options that can be used by service users according to the desired needs. The service menu provided by the Inaportnet website is available on the left side of the page and an information/announcement column is also available at the top of the Dashboard view. If adjusted to the theory of e-service quality according to Ribbink et. al (2004) it can be concluded that the dimensions of Ease of Use (Convenience) and E-Scape (Display) in the appearance of the Inaportnet website have met the needs of service users. This is evidenced by the easy access of the Inaportnet website page, as well as the Dashboard page which has menus that can be selected according to the needs of service users. Whereas other dimensions such as Customization, Responsiveness, and Assurance are not yet available on the Inaportnet website, so researchers must conduct in-depth research to measure the quality of online ship maneuvering permit services. In connection with the problems that have been stated above, for this reason the researcher is interested in conducting research with the title "Quality of Service for Ship Motion Permits Online at the Tanjung Perak Surabaya Main Harbormaster Office".

RESEARCH METHOD

In this study using qualitative research methods. Qualitative method is research to describe and analyze phenomena, events, beliefs, attitudes, and social activities individually or in groups. The qualitative method is a collection of methods to analyze and understand more deeply the meaning of some individuals or groups considered as a humanitarian or social problem (Creswell, 2015). Judging from the type of data the research approach used in this study is a qualitative approach. As for what is meant by qualitative research, namely research that intends to understand the phenomenon of what is experienced by research subjects holistically, and by means of descriptions in the form of words and language, in a special natural context and by utilizing various scientific methods (Moleong, 2017).

Data analysis according to Sugiyono (2018) is the process of systematically searching for and compiling data obtained from interviews, field notes and documentation, by organizing data into categories, describing them into units, synthesizing them, compiling them into patterns, selecting which ones are important and what will be learned, and draw conclusions so that they are easily understood by themselves and others. Meanwhile, according to Moleong (2017) data analysis is the process of organizing and sorting data into patterns, categories, and basic descriptive units so that themes can be found and working hypotheses can be formulated as suggested by the data.

Qualitative research data, data obtained from various sources, using various data collection techniques (triangulation) and carried out continuously resulting in very high data variations. The data analysis technique used by the research uses the Miles and Huberman model. According to Miles and Huberman in Sugiyono's book (2018) data analysis in qualitative research is carried out when data collection takes place, and after completing data collection within a certain period. Activities in qualitative data analysis are carried out interactively and continuously until complete, so that the data is saturated. Miles and Huberman offer a general pattern of analysis by following an interactive model.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research is a qualitative descriptive study regarding the quality of online Ship Motion Permit services at the Tanjung Perak Surabaya Main Harbormaster office, so researchers are trying to show and describe it. The results of this study are in the form

of data obtained through observation, interviews, and documentation. The assessment of the service quality of the Online Ship Motion Permit at the Tanjung Perak Surabaya Main Harbormaster Office was studied based on the theory of electronic service quality (e-service quality) by Ribbink et. al (2004) with five dimensions, namely: Ease of Use, E-Scape, Customization, Responsiveness, and Assurance. The results and qualitative analysis on each dimension can be described with the following explanation:

1. Ease of Use (Convenience)

Ease of Use (convenience) refers to the convenience for users in finding information and the ease of access available, this is an important reason for service users to choose services online. In this study the dimension of Ease of Use (convenience) is determined from the convenience of service users to find information on the Inaportnet website or application regarding the services needed, and the ease of service users in accessing the Inaportnet website or application for the need for ship maneuvering permits based on systems, mechanisms and procedure. The dimension of Ease of Use (convenience) in online ship maneuvering permit services through the Inaportnet website or application shows that the quality of service is optimal, this is evidenced by several results of interviews with informants who stated that service users can easily access the Inaportnet website or application in the process of submitting a ship maneuvering permit online, service users do not need to take a long time to access the Inaportnet application if the internet connection is smooth, there is a menu of instructions and information available to make it easier for service users. Having an online service system greatly facilitates the work of shipping agents/service users in terms of ship maneuvering permits, compared to conventional services because the time required is shorter when done online.

2. E-Scape (View)

The appearance of features and menus on websites or applications must have a structured aesthetic to make it easier for users to access them. Site or application design must be similar to conventional services because it will affect the perception of service users. The appearance design of a site or application plays an important role so that service users use services online. In this study, the indicator for measuring the E-Scape dimension (Display) is that the website or application Inaportnet has a display that is appropriate and easily accessible to service users regarding applications for ship maneuvering permits online, and service users can access the Inaportnet website or application clearly and easily. .

Based on the results of the interviews obtained from the informants, the E-Scape dimension (Appearance) in online ship maneuvering permit services through the website or the Inaportnet application shows optimal service quality. This is evidenced by the fact that service users can easily access the Inaportnet website or application regarding applications for ship maneuvering permits online, for the appearance in terms of design, color, and navigation that have been fulfilled in the Inaportnet application. The functions on the menu available in the application are very simple and uncomplicated so that service users can understand them easily, and the navigation system in the Inaportnet application is very easy to use, making it easier for shipping agents to apply for ship operating permits online.

3. Customization

Customization refers to adjusting the level of service provided by a site or application to the wishes and needs of each user. The Customization dimension refers to the success of the website or application in conveying its products or services and correcting errors when users access the website or application. In this study the indicators for measuring the dimensions of Customization are the website or application Inaportnet can function properly and has the ability to correct errors that occur during the process of applying for a ship maneuvering permit online, available complaints, suggestions and input services on the website or application Inaportnet to respond to service user complaints.

The results obtained by the researcher through interviews with informants show that the dimensions of Customization in online ship maneuvering permit services through the website or the Inaportnet application show that service quality is not optimal. There is a menu that is not yet available in the Inaportnet application, namely the complaint and suggestion service menu that is not in the Inaportnet application, service boxes and complaints are still provided at the PPSA (One-Stop Service Center) Kesyahbandaran Utama Tanjung Perak Surabaya office, the menu for correcting data is also not available in the Inaportnet application and if an error occurs during the data input process, only a red warning appears at that time. Service users have not fully experienced online services, they still have to visit the Kesyahbandaran service office which is very inefficient because it requires time and effort.

4. Responsiveness (Responsiveness)

Responsiveness refers to the willingness to assist service users when accessing the Inaportnet site or application such as answering questions, responding to complaints, and overcoming problems faced by service users as well as the availability of alternative communication channels. In this study, the indicators for measuring the Responsiveness dimension are SPOGK Operators (Ship Motioning Approval Letters) providing services or responses to service users when encountering obstacles in accessing the Inaportnet website or application, and SPOGK Operators (Ship Motions Approval Letters).) provide services and respond quickly and precisely in accordance with the needs related to the application for a ship operating permit online.

Based on the results of the interviews obtained from the informants, the Responsiveness dimension in online ship maneuvering permit services through the website or the Inaportnet application shows optimal service quality. It is known that the SPOGK Operator (Approval for Ship Movement) is always ready and alert in providing directions to service users and always responds quickly if problems occur related to the application for ship processing permits online, SPOGK Operators provide solutions to service users regarding problems that occur when experiencing difficulties in accessing the Inaportnet application, and the Main Harbormaster of Tanjung Perak Surabaya also provides information services needed for service users.

5. Assurance (Guarantee)

The Assurance dimension is the privacy or security of service users, which refers to the protection of personal information and data. Guarantee that user data will not be spread to any party and personal data information is guaranteed security. In this study the indicators used to measure the Assurance dimension are the website or Inaportnet application that is proven to be trusted to store personal data for service users, and online services in the process of applying for a ship's maneuvering license that are carried out properly and smoothly can build trust and confidence. to service users.

Based on the results of the interviews obtained from the informants, the dimension of assurance in the online ship maneuvering permit service through the website or the Inaportnet application shows optimal service quality. Service users trust and believe that data and information can be properly protected, each user who accesses the Inaportnet application has their own account such as a username and password, data security and protection has been systemically designed within the Inaportnet application so that it is able to maintain the privacy of service users. Thus service users feel confident and have confidence in data security when they access the Inaportnet application in the case of an online application for a ship maneuvering permit.

The following table shows the results of the analysis of the Quality of Service for Ship Motion Permits Online at the Tanjung Perak Surabaya Main Harbormaster Office, explained in the table below:

Table 1. Matrix Analysis of the Quality of Service for Ship Motion Permits Online at the Tanjung Perak Main Harbormaster Office, Surabaya

No.	Indicator	Analysis results
1	<i>Ease of Use</i>	<p>The results of the study show that the dimensions of Ease of Use in the online ship processing permit application process through the Inaportnet application based on the results of interviews with informants are as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Inaportnet application can be accessed easily, service users don't need a long time if the internet connection is smooth • The Inaportnet application is very easy to use because there is a menu of instructions and information in it • The online process for submitting a ship maneuvering license is faster than conventional services

2	<i>E-Scape</i>	<p>The results of the study show that the E-Scape dimension (View) for the Quality of Service for Ship Motion Permits Online, has</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • shows good service quality. This is evidenced by the results of interviews with informants as follows: • Appearance in terms of design, color and navigation has been fulfilled for service users • The menu functions in the Inaportnet application are also simple and uncomplicated so service users can understand them easily • The navigation system in the Inaportnet application is also very easy to use, thus facilitating the work of shipping agents in the process of applying for ship maneuvering permits online
3	<i>Customization</i>	<p>The results of the study show that the Customization dimension in the online ship processing permit application process through the Inaportnet application has not shown good service quality. The following are the results of the analysis by researchers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complaint and suggestion services are not yet available in the Inaportnet application • Service and complaint boxes are still provided at the PPSA (One-Stop Service Center) office of Kesyahbandaran Utama Tanjung Perak Surabaya • The menu for correcting data is not yet available in the user-specific Inaportnet Application, there is only a red warning that appears when an error occurs during data input
4	<i>Responsiveness</i>	<p>The results of the study show that the Responsiveness dimension in the process of applying for ship maneuvering permits online through the Inaportnet application has shown good service quality. The following are the results of the analysis by researchers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SPOGK operators (Ship Motions Approval Letters) are always ready and alert in providing services, directions, and responses when problems occur • SPOGK operators provide solutions related to problems that occur in the process of applying for an online motion permit • The Main Harbormaster of Tanjung Perak Surabaya provides services and information needed related to the process of submitting an online motion permit
5	<i>Assurance</i>	<p>The results of the study show that the Assurance dimension in the online ship processing permit application process through the Inaportnet application has shown good service quality. The following are the results of the analysis by researchers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Every user who accesses the Inaportnet application has their own account, such as a username and password • Security and protection of service user data has been systemically designed within the Inaportnet application so as to maintain the privacy of service users • Service users feel confident that the online processing permit application process does not take a long time

Source: Data processed by researchers (2023)

Supporting Factors and Inhibiting Factors

On the Quality of Service for Ship Motion Permits Online at the Tanjung Perak Surabaya Main Harbormaster Office, there are supporting factors and inhibiting factors, as follows:

1. Supporting Factors

- a. Applications for ship maneuvering permits online which are accessed through the Inaportnet application will be very easy to use if the internet connection is smooth. So far, service users have never complained about this because the internet network is adequate, so online services are more helpful for their work.
- b. For every application for a ship maneuvering permit online, service users can directly access the Inaportnet application to find out the results of each submission that have been verified by officers. Service users no longer need to wait for information by phone or have to come directly to the PPSA (One-Stop Service Center) Kesyahbandaran Utama Tanjung Perak Surabaya Office.
- c. The Tanjung Perak Surabaya Main Harbormaster Office periodically (once a month) holds a coffee morning event with shipping agents (service users), this is done to build trust and carry out socialization if there are new changes in online services, especially ship maneuvering permit services.

2. Inhibiting Factors

- a. The internet network is slow or when the Inapoertnet application is having trouble/errors, this causes the data input process to take a very long time, especially if the data is entered in large amounts.
- b. There is no data change menu and complaint service available in the Inaportnet application. Service users must come directly to the PPSA (One-Stop Service Center) office of Kesyahbandaran Utama Tanjung Perak Surabaya to submit complaints and suggestions in the suggestion box provided.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion conducted by researchers regarding the Quality of Online Ship Motion Permit Service at the Tanjung Perak Surabaya Main Harbormaster Office, which was measured using the theory of electronic service quality (e-service quality) by Ribbink et. al (2004) can be concluded:

1. Measuring the Quality of Service Quality for Ship Motion Permits Online at the Tanjung Perak Surabaya Main Harbormaster Office using the theory of electronic service quality (e-service quality) by Ribbink et. al (2004) through 5 (five) dimensions, namely: Ease of Use (Convenience), E-Scape (Appearance), Customization (Adjustments), Responsiveness (Responsiveness), and Assurance (Assurance) have not shown optimal service quality. It is said that it is not optimal because the Customization dimension has not met the needs of service users, this is evidenced by the service menu and complaints not yet available in the Inaportnet application and the service box is still provided manually at the PPSA (One-Stop Service Center) Kesyahbandaran Utama Tanjung Perak Surabaya office. The menu for correcting data if an error occurs during data input is also not available in the Inaportnet application, there is only a red warning when an error occurs during data input so service users have to repeat the process from the beginning.
2. Supporting factors in measuring the Quality of Service for Ship Motion Permits Online at the Tanjung Perak Surabaya Main Harbormaster Office include: a smooth internet connection network, to find out the application process has been verified by service user officers, simply access the Inaportnet application to see the results, and the Main Kesyahbandaran Tanjung Perak Surabaya periodically once a month holds coffee morning with shipping agents (service users) this is done to build trust and conduct outreach if there are new changes in terms of applying for ship operating permits online.

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